

12:30 - 14:00	Session 2: Connecting the Near-Field and Deep Field View of Galaxy Formation	Chair: Preethi Nair (U. Alabama)
12:30 - 13:00	2a Invited Talk: James Bullock (UCI)	Invited Talk
13:00 - 13:15	2b Ben Williams (UW)	Surveying Nearby Galaxies with Roman
13:15 - 13:30	2c Kristen McQuinn (Rutgers)	The Roman Space Telescope: A Pathway to Measuring Accurate Distances to Every Galaxy in the Nearby Universe
13:30 - 13:45	2d Raja GuhaThakurta (UCSC)	Three Roman Telescope Science Cases for Local Volume Galaxies
13:45 - 14:00	2e Sarah Pearson (Flatiron Inst.)	Stellar Streams from Globular Clusters in the Local Universe

Session 2 live captioning on Monday, 5 October 2020

Preethi Nair: Welcome to session 2. Connecting with near field -- my name is Preethi. I am a faculty member of the University of Alabama. I will be the chair of the session. Just a recap of guidelines for this session. We have one invited to talk and for contributive the talks. I will give a five minute warning for the invited talk in 2 minutes remaining for regular talks. I will also let you know when time is up. For participants and those of you who have questions, please ask your questions on slack. Please ask them as they come to you. Other participants can upload your question using the thumbs up emoji. I will ask the questions during the Q&A time. All right, so let's get started. Our first speaker is **James Bullock** from the University of California Irvine. Please share your screen and take it away.

James: Okay, great. Thanks, everyone. It's a great pleasure to be able to present to you today. This session is about connecting near field and deep field in understanding the galaxy formation evolution. This is a pretty broad subject. When I sat down to do this, I realize there was no way I could come close to discussing all the things that Nancy Grace Roman space telescope will do to enable us to do this deep field near field connection. I thought I would start by talking about definitions. What do we mean by near field, for example? the thing that is remarkable about this telescope is the near field for this telescope which normally thought of as where you can do resolve star studies, something like ten mega parsecs which is really amazing. We are talking about panda style maps. 31 out to ten mega parsecs. Ben Williams I think it's going to talk a lot about that aspects of the local volume in that space. You are talking about galaxy structure with individual stars, stellar halos and satellites. Mapping the accretion history of these galaxies is going to be amazing. When I thought I would do instead was to sort of go back to a more traditional discussion of near field and really talk about the Milky Way. It's a way to narrow and what I was going to talk about. The Milky Way, it's going to be amazing to have complete surveys of red club stars deep into the galactic bulge. There's going to be a lot of cool science that will come with that. Even with the Milky Way stellar halo, you are talking about finding the main sequence turnoff 400 Killa parsecs throughout the Milky Way or in chunks of the Milky Way. Something like 1.5 mega parsecs. This is going to open things wide for a lot of interesting studies in the Milky Way in the local group. Also, proper motions and whether that is internal or orbital motions for galactic satellites is going to be a bit transformative here. So, the way I'm going to frame my connections will be with these kind of capabilities in

mind. Now, let me go to deep field. When I'm going to do is talk about deep field with three definitions of deep. First, I'm gonna talk about red shift 2. The red shift two is a really interesting Epoque and galaxy evolution. I like to think of it as the Epoque of unsettled disks. Things have clumped and if they can. Lots of feedback and lots of outflows at this time. But the interesting thing is there is a residue left over in the Milky Way itself that we can begin to study. Then we have higher redshifts to think of the Epoque in the first galaxies. This is a hot topic of interest. It's a place where the Milky Way really shed light. Finally, a red shift 10 to the 15. What I mean by that is the nature of dark matter itself. Let me start with the nature of dark matter. So, we think for example if the dark matter was a wimp, we would think it froze out some time when the universe was about ten in temperature. That something like ten to the 15 in red shift. There's a lot of implications for that. If you have a standard wimp type dark matter particle. We have pretty good predictions for what the universe made of cold dark matter collision list dark matter would look like. In one of the fairly robust predictions is dark matter halos should because be. One over R, small R. Many galaxies in the universe don't look that way. Many of them have course. This has been around basically as long as CDM simulations have had high enough resolution to predict what the slope should be. It was recognized that that did not really look like a galaxy. These days we know that feedback can solve a lot of these problems. In the middle of dark matter halo fairly robustly as long as you forming up stars. If you don't forming up stars and specifically if you are a dwarf galaxy that has about a million stars, very difficult for feedback to make course. If you play around with the nature of dark matter, if it is self interacting of some ultralight scalar field, he can produce without feedback. These are really great laboratories for testing and constraining the nature of dark matter. The problem is that these galaxy supported traditionally. You can't measure a rotation curve. You have to figure out other ways to measure the masses. Typically, the way you measure mass -- if you have a line upside velocities, there is a degeneracy between the anisotropy of the stars in the orbits. And that mass profile that you can extract. This is a well-known degeneracy known for a long time. It turns out that there is one mass, there is one radius or a dwarf galaxy that you actually can measure the mass fairly robustly and at a dispersion anisotropy. That is roughly the radius where the long slope tracer profile is minus 3. That is close to the half-life of the galaxy. Measure a line of sight philosophy dispersion and use this simple formula here to determine what the mass is at that radius. For example, you use this mass when you predict the failed problem and do other things like predictions and observations of the specific mass. This specific mass is a mass at a given radius. It's not telling you if the slope is a cusp or a corporate this may soon change as we start to get more and more proper motion measurements, internal proper motion measurements for galaxies. Here are some examples. Two papers where they actually measured proper emotion and philosophy dispersion's in the Plano Vizcaya for a couple of different galaxies. Draco is a very interesting object because it is very low mass. So it is interesting is if you have tangential philosophies, you can derive a different asset estimator. There is another magic radius for tangential philosophies. Is actually where the long scope of the tracer profile is minus 2. The important thing here is if you have proper emotions in the plane of the sky even if you don't have that many, you can still measure dispersion. You can fairly robustly measure the mass at a specific radius. Also these galaxies, if you have tangential emotions, you can do that, you already have the line of sight motions. You can put together and measure a slope. Right now, if you take the current data, they are consistent with and FW fits reasonably accurately. But the error bars are large on that. As we do this for more of our galaxies with more and more stars, this is going to be a very interesting way of testing the nature of dark matter. That is an example of that kind of thing that you can do at red shift attended the 15. that may go with a different definition of deep field. Let's look at redshifts six. There is a great desire to understand what the stellar mass function or the luminosity function looks like at these higher redshifts. There's implications for knowing what the first galaxies are like. This is a quest that people have been after for a long time. Even with a front tier fields right now, you just can't get crazy deep. Getting to sort of things that probably will turn into a dwarf. But you are not really getting all the way down the mass function. But I would like to make a claim which is that we have actually already found the first galaxies -- we've actually found -- as you probably know, we have discovered 40 very low stellar mass core galaxies orbiting around the Milky Way. As far as we can tell, these things are made of uniformly ancient stellar populations. Probably had their stellar formation wiped out in one way or another by cosmic randomization itself. And I would argue -- at least I had the gas cap possibly, these things are a fair sample of the early universe. As we are able to discover more and more of these things both within the Milky Way, deeper way out within Calipari out into the Milky Way and even may be around other galaxies as well, we will be gaining a sample of objects that we know collapsed very early on. I wanted to show you this picture which is a result that is improper by Alex Lazar. This is a small chunk of a cosmological volume called firebox that is simulated and very high resolution. Enough that you can resolve many halos. This is, I think, the things that are colored in black are objects that will become ultra-faint dwarf candidates. They will be some halos of Milky Way's that have very low masses. There's about about a hundred per Milky Way. This is where these things are at redshifts six. The stuff is in red is everything else with a comparable

sample of collapsed objects. At the red it's all field halos at redshifts six. Black is stuff that's going to turn into an ultra-faint dwarf galaxy. One other thing that is very interesting about this is if you look at the formation times of these things, they are reasonably consistent. The black and the black man's are the medium proxy formation time for these ultra-faint dwarf things that will become ultra-faint dwarf satellites. The gray is scattering in this proxy. The red are all the field halos. As you can see, there's really not that much of a bias. You might've been concerned if you see an ultra-faint that is some side of bias progenitor or a biased descendant of the first galaxy population, the first collapsed population. That does not seem to be the case by measures like this. What this means is they provide a really interesting laboratory for constraining objects as they were. These things typically kind of stop forming stars sometime after C of six. You have the frozen in relics the early universe that don't seem to be particularly bias. In that sense, they are representative of the early universe and therefore may be particularly interesting. Finally, let me move to a third definition of deep field. It is redshifts 2 what I called the Epoque of unsettled disks and outflows. Galaxies around red shift 2 look kind of messed up. They are a bit clumpy in their star forming regions. They have pretty significant outflows at this time just because of the nature of the universe. We think of course those outflows are fundamental to galaxy formation itself. Without this kind of feedback, you really would have a very different galaxy population of zero. What we can do is use a simulation to try to give us sense as of how you connect the very early times 2008 times with a galaxy like the Milky Way. When I'm showing you is an image of the build up of the Milky Way size galaxy. This is a cosmological zoom simulation of a galaxy simulated with fire to physics. This is done by a student at UCI. This image. What you see here is that this is an edge on view of what this galaxy looks like at 11 billion years ago, 85, 2.7, and zero. Easy of the classic picture of the way that galaxy has evolved and been building up over the last decade or so is that these galaxies form inside out and upside down. The first things to be calm and place are sort of the central bulge region. As time goes on, you start to make kind of a thick disk. And then, as a function of time, he began to build that then disk after that thick disk. This is very different for example than a classic picture that you have thin disks, something had said and heats it up to make that thick disk. What you generally see is things are very chaotic and they began to settle down with time. This means that if you could peer into the inner bolts, you really are looking at those very first Epoque so galaxy formation for our galaxy. You could begin testing models. How you measure that thick disk population and that then disk population as well. You're really tracing galactic assembly that way. Here is the star formation history of this galaxy as simulated with fire. And the stars along the x-axis are where we have made these images. And you note that I very early times, star formation is extremely bursty. it turns out that's related to outflow. You have settling down phase. As you are peering into the core of the galaxy, you are peering into this bursty chaotic phase that we think most galaxies like the Milky Way experienced. Now, interestingly, during this bursty phase, you have a lot of outflow. One of the really, I think I'm a very interesting things over the last few years is evidence that in these molecular outflows that we have known for some time, there is growing evidence that star formation is actually occurring in the outflow. And here is for example a paper. He found that more than 30% of the outflows that they picked out your standard gaseous outflows, 30% of those things have stellar outflows associated with those gaseous outflows. Something in the outflow is triggering star formation. The outflow rates can be very high, up to 30% of star formation rate in these galaxies. Why am I talking about this? If you think about it, if you got a galactic stellar outflow, shooting stars coming out from the galaxy, these stellar outflow rates are something like 150 kilometers per second. That rate is enough to get you out of the disk, but is not high enough that it's going to escape the galaxy forever. What will happen as those things fall back in. And if you just look at this cartoon, that is a stellar halo orbit. This is not -- these are not stars that are going to be confined to the inner galaxy. These are stars that are shot out and not on down and will orbit and plunging orbit. Akin to stellar halo orbits. This is a halo population that in principle can go incredibly far out. The fire simulations like I was showing you earlier show this effect. What we have is a zoom in on a disk as it is forming stars at some red shift snapshot. What you see is sort of a mock Hubble image. On top of that in pinky as the local star formation rate. And what you see happening is there is this clustered supernova super bubble that starts to be created. On the edge of that super bubble, you have star formation that is triggered. Since the gas is already on its way out, they launch out. They can fly out to the very edges of the galaxy. We see this is fairly common in our galaxies. In fact, if you measure the fractional stars in the stellar halo's these galaxies, as a function of a radius, you find that once you get to radius of 100 to 200 per second, the fractional stars born in outflows grows to a fairly substantial fraction. 40% of the very outer halo of these stars are actually born in the central galaxy and shot out in these outflows. And what is very interesting about the Nancy Grace Roman possibility here is that we could start to see main sequence turnoff stars in the outer stellar halo they could be representative of these events. If so, it is definitely a way of testing and constraining the idea that these stellar outflows are possible. This is a different picture by the way than the way we traditionally have thought about that halo made of accreted dwarf galaxies that come in. But these accreted -- the accreted stellar halo is clumpy

especially at large radius. There is a lot of structure that you expect to be there from accreted dwarf stars there is the diffuse population that exists for the outflow stars. So we think that these shooting stars, the outflow stars will be metal rich alpha enhanced and smoothly distributed to the accreted stellar halo dwarf galaxy. This is a crazy idea, the idea that you would make stars in outflows and they would matter this much in the outer stellar halo. That's why it's important to test. I don't think that all models would predict this. You really need to have star formation triggered in outflow for this to happen. That kind of physics is hard to simulate. A could be that this prediction is wrong. If it is true, and gives you an insight into the nature of galaxy formation and galaxy evolution using your field studies distinct on anything that we thought was possible even ten years ago. Just another example of the fun stuff that this telescope level will enable. 5 minutes remaining. Great, just about to finish up. I will have lots of time. To take questions and move on. So let me just summarize what I talked about. What I said is, I'm going to limit near field to the Milky Way, and its halo and leave the other nine mega parsec sphere to others in the talk. The first thing I talked about was red shift of 10 to the 15. And the nature of dark matter. And talked about how in the coming years if we are able to measure tangential velocity dispersions with some regularity, there is a quick and easy way to measure the mass within a robust radius of those measurements. This should enable, we hope, fairly robust tests of the cusp or issue when combined with line of sight philosophies. I talked about red shift six. There are lots of stuff associated with near field, deep field, and the space. I thought it was kind of fun -- I really think that the thing for us are pretty good and representative of what the first galaxy has look like at these early times. We've got a bunch of them nearby. They are hard-to-find and very faint, et cetera, et cetera. The prospects are pretty compelling for easing these things as a remnant of the early universe. Finally, I went to red shift 2 where you have this inside out, upside down galaxy formation prediction. And we have all of this evidence that galaxies undergo this settling with time that has been building up over the years. It is going to be fantastic ways of testing these pictures in understanding the origin and why our galaxy is born thick and then become thin over time. Different simulations predict different reasons why this might be. By having deeper probes into the core of the galaxy, it will allow us to test these ideas with more detail. With that, I think I will stop it. Thank.

Max: I just unmuted Preethi. If you are having trouble, I can ask questions of James. Okay, James, I'm going to ask one of the questions while Preethi is getting back online here. This one is from Ryan. How well can we constrain the star formation histories of the ultra faint dwarfs and in particular when they shut off their star formations?

James: It is a great question. Right now with the best results star studies with HST, you know, you can get there within a couple of billion years. It's very hard to know at 10 billion years, as it 10 or 9 or 11? Right now, you kind of know they shut down some time before red shift 2, for example. And, you know, my understanding is that it is very hard to know if it is 13.2 versus 12 versus whatever. Go ahead. Go ahead, James. The context of this question I think is, can you test this idea where these things shut down or not? I would just say that in a lot of our simulations, our galaxies are not shut down. At the formation does not start. It plays a crucial role. It shuts down gas secretion. There is still cold gas in the ultra faint. Only after some time does it sort of wealth quenched by feedback. It is basically a combination of organization shuts down in the flow, and then it sort of then subsequently itself and she is because there is no new info of gas to build that next generation of stars. We will have ultra faint dwarf galaxies all of our ultra faints are quenched by Z of 0. Many of them actually stop forming stars closer to red shift 2 rather than red shift 6 because of this.

Preethi: I assume that somebody took over asking questions for you when I was tossed out. And so, the next question here asks "we have a sense of how essential black hole growth would work with inside out, upside down scenario. Does it have a different concept of how it merges the galaxy structure?"

James: That's a good question. I think, you know, one thing I should say is it is not that mergers never matter. But when they do matter, you end up not having a Milky Way. I guess that is maybe a short answer for these inside out, upside down pictures. You know, the bolts is not really -- that thick disk is not really made by a single merger event. It's a classic picture, et cetera. A question of how a black hole would grow in a galaxy like the one I was showing compared to something with a much more robust black hole, you know that might very well how to do more closely with merger history. And so to be honest, we have not looked at that, because I would just say that those sort of supermassive black hole feeding in the firing simulations is still in development in a way that sort of I would want to use it for a Milky Way simulation. But it is a very good question I think for other galaxies like M31 where the black hole is bigger. Of course each one looks a lot different than the Milky Way as well. A good question.

Preethi: There's actually a lot of discussion on slack. If you can login at the end to answer the others, here's one more. "How can you use Roman to prove that a significant fraction of the halo stars were ejected? Or could you?"

James: I think it's going to be hard. I think what we would like to do eventually is measure -- let me back up. One of the things you may have thought is that the orbital properties of Z of 0 stars would be different if they were born and outflows versus accreted. As a population, they are not. By that time they have gone around a few times, they look the same. However, there is much more structure in the phase space of treated stuff. So you predict at a much higher fraction of the outer halo if it was made entirely of accreted things would be structured in phase space. And that is something that this telescope is really going to enable. And so, what you would predict on top of that is there is this background smooth population that is alpha enhanced that would stand out there and you would be able to see it. It's really crucial that you get way out. I'm talking 200 or 300K PC which is deeper than anyone can go right now with the standard surveys. I think it will be crucial to those kind of tests.

Preethi: Thanks, James. We are at that time. Thank you very much. Everybody said they really enjoyed this talk.

Our next speaker -- one second. Our next speaker is Ben Williams. If you could share your slide. This is **Ben Williams** from the University of Washington. Take it away.

Ben: Hi, everybody. I'm a P.I. of the nearby galaxies investigation team. I want to talk to you a little bit about what we have been doing to think about what we can learn from Roman from observations of nearby galaxies. You know, we look at nearby galaxies because we see them as critical for astrophysics. They give us this detailed view and the context of these processes going on within galaxies simultaneously. They are sensitive to galaxy evolution and cosmology from James' great overview. They anchor our knowledge of complex sources for interpreting more distant galaxies that we can't resolve. The cover of wide range galaxy properties. The sample is large and has star formation rates and star formation intensities. If you get subdivided for your specific science goals. The Roman space telescope is perfect for this kind of work because a near field is inherently wide-field. As soon as you move things in close, you need really high resolution in order to take advantage of the fact that you've got these galaxies more nearby. You need to have high sensitivity in order to go deep enough to get those individual processes. You need the stereo wide-field. Roman delivers in all of these areas. Another way of looking at this is if you look at the sample of nearby galaxies inside of 10 make up our and look at their sizes, you see how well suited the Roman field of view size is for covering a large fraction of them. And in particular, you look for these blue dots that are larger in the field of view that lie an absolute magnitude sense. You will see that most of the brighter galaxies, the ones that dominate most grid shift surveys are in that size regime in the sky. We will learn an enormous amount about the galaxies that we are usually studying the most once we have this great coverage with Roman. And, one example that is often shown is M31. I have to at least quickly go through how difficult it is to survey a galaxy like M31 at the level of precision and the level of resolution you want with Hubble where it is not just a matter of yeah, it takes a lot of Hubble pointing to cover it, but is a matter of the logistics. Even not just the fact that you have to point the telescope a lot, but because it takes so much time to schedule these kinds of things, this took several years of effort. You look at something like this. The reason you are doing it is so that you can observe the stars. Anyone could take a picture of M31. Only Hubble can do it at that kind of resolution where you get the stars out. And you can do all of that much more quickly with Roman. That is a very common example. Even relatively far away, you get small amount of coverage. This is the example that James shows briefly at the beginning of his talk where if you look at a galaxy like M1, you get a small pencil beam through even that with HST and it an individual pointing. Not only do you get with something like Roman this coverage of the main body of the galaxy, but you also get a halo and information about the stellar halo the power of which James already talked about and I will talk more about an imminent. And you get these resolved stars. This is an example of being able to resolve stars in this disk. You can also gain access to the stellar halo and a way that you really can't from the ground. If you look from the ground, you can go as deep as you want. Even in good seeing, and it's very difficult to see what is a star and a background galaxy. When you get this high resolution that is enabled by something like Roman, you can resolve out those stars and be able to not only determine the service brightness, the effective service brightness of those stellar populations but be able to use them to constrain things. Look for the kinds of effects that James was talking about. And it is really that being able to get those stars tells the whole story. And

that is largely because the possible record of these features. And their colors and luminosity's really tell us something about their age and distributions. Because of that, they tagged the ages of past events along with their associated passives and energies. You learn about how whatever you are detecting formed and evolved. So, we have been putting a lot of our efforts into simulating Roman galaxy observations. We can see what the powers will be. To be able to optimize our observing strategy as well as our science that we will pull out. This is one of our earliest ones where we looked at Hubble mosaic of M31. This is several pointing us with Hubble. You can easily monitor the stars. A relatively large area. What we do is we take those double data and we measure the stars and put them into the simulation tools which include the tool developed by space telescope and create simulated Roman images. Now, and this particular case, and it was than one detectors worth, all of that effort to reduce all of that and put it into the Roman simulations. But it was a good start. And then, we were able to create sort of this mock simulation of sort of a near field science overview that went into one of the white papers for the survey where we just short of it showed that you can look at, you know, globular clusters, nearby galaxies. You can find a small faint dwarf galaxies and the halos of these nearby galaxies as well as other structures. And then, the next thing we decided to make a simulation of was the actual survey. In this particular case, the photometry was already available because the team had produced it. It was surveyed in the infrared. We had reasonable proxies for the WFIRST bands. We propped down some reasonable pointing of Roman and simulated an observation of all the stars in that field from those catalogs. It came out looking something like M31. That was a good start. This has also been really useful for the project. These kinds of simulations allow us a chance to test what kind of observing strategies will work best for pulling science out of a nearby galaxy observation. Ideally, we want to use this for studying halo structures of galaxies farther out. You can see this is what the Roman footprint looks like on this pandas map of the stellar halo of M31. These things are huge. And luckily, M31 is well studied and well observed, because it is close by and can be done from the ground. We can do this for many galaxies farther away. The idea is to be able to constrain something about the accretion histories of these galaxies and how they formed. And they will also be some more talks about stellar halos. James has talked a little bit about it. But the idea being for these slightly farther away halos that the sizes and shapes and brightness and numbers of these streams and structures that are in these halos that are very difficult to observe from the ground can often be seen in Star counselor should be able to seen in star count data once we are able to resolve the stars with Roman. Running out of time? 2 minutes remaining. Great. We have been looking into doing this using the fire simulation. Robin Anderson has put together this great software for taking the fire simulations and creating actual mock catalogs of the stellar populations within those simulations. We can take those stellar catalogs and use those as our input for our simulated images. And then, in those images, we know where the stars are and where the background galaxies are. We can hone our analysis techniques to be able to optimize finding the stars. Once we make catalogs of those stars, we can test things like automated identification of streams and shells. Sarah is going to talk more about those kinds of automated structure finding techniques. We are also going to be able to test finding dwarf galaxies, faint dwarf satellites. Like James was talking about in more distinct galaxies. And the mass functions of these galaxies are sensitive probes of dark matter. We will also be able to resolve clusters out too far distances as far out as the Virgo cluster. Raja is going to talk a little about that. Those globular clusters are great for a follow-up work as well as probing the early epoch galaxy assembly. They get the stellar populations because we have identified all of the stars. We get the stellar populations and specific populations. We will be able to measure the red Giant branch and find short-lived high luminosity phases of stars. Christie is going to talk about the tip of the red giant branch type measurements just coming up right after me. So, we can use all of these things to maximize the value of the survey of nearby galaxies including sample selection and the distance distribution and depth of area and which filters you want to observe, what kind of scheduling you want to do. Potential promotion studies and most nearby ones. And what kind of data products are going to be the most useful for us and the community. I will stop there. I do have some information about other ongoing projects that you can ask me about during the questions if you want. But I don't want to go over.

Preethi: More questions coming in on slack. If you can answer questions later, they would be great. We have time for one question. "How important is Astro metric information and proper motions for some of this work where they're from Guyana, Institute measurements or other platforms?"

Ben: Proper motions like James was saying for the Galactic satellites will be extremely useful. There has been a lot of work going on thinking about that. I think Robin and James both have been thinking about proper motion. For constraining orbits. There's also the possibility for some of the more distant local group galaxies that could be potential for proper motion measurements for things like M31 and M33 which have already gotten measurements

from HST. Certainly larger having that over larger fields of youth couldn't hurt. But it is unclear whether we will be able to do that kind of scheduling depends on what people propose for their programs if we can -- if it is going to be done with a 5-year time base to have our ability to do proper motions or not.

Preethi: Thanks a lot. That is the end of this time.

Apologies for the technical delay. Our next speaker is **Kristen McQuinn**. I will let her introduce her talk.

Kristen: Thank you. Roman is going to be this amazing pathway to measuring accurate distances to every nearby galaxy. Throughout much of the universe, we use velocity based information to measure distances. In the nearby universe, velocity based distances are subject to significant uncertainties. I mean velocity based distances can be off by a factor of a few to several. Any property such as the luminosity masses depend on the distance squared are really simply just inaccurate. At the nearby universe we use alternative measures for distance. And arguably, the most efficient and accurate method is the tip of the giant red bridge standard candle which can resolve stars imaging. With Roman's angular resolution and sensitivity in the Widefield community surveys that are being planned, we will really have a data archive that will enable accurate data sets. The pressure of whether the red giant method looks like. On the left is a image from Hubble where you can resolve the individual stars. Running an image like this, you can create a color magnitude diagram. We have luminosity of stars measured in the filter which is a band equivalent filter is a function of stellar color. The main feature in this colored magnitude diagram is a red giant branch. Burning hydrogen and shell around a helium core as the helium core mass increases, immensely, it will ignite helium. As a helium flash moves off the RGB in luminosity and color leaving behind a pretty sharp discontinuity that is highlighted with a purple arrow. You can see on the right panel is being plotted the stellar luminosity function. It's readily measured by the change in the number of stars at that luminosity. This is work being done. Okay, we typically do these in Hubble. In particular, it's an excellent tracer because the luminosity of stars at the tip of a modest dependency on luminosity. It's well calibrated. It can be done to nearby galaxies with 5% precision or better. They have managed with Roman -- here are the examples of things we have done with Hubble on these high quality distances. They are sort of an ingredient for understanding galaxies. On the left are some images from a couple of different programs that I've had in the last two years measuring distances to spiral galaxies, ellipticals and a few dozen low mass galaxies. Getting accurate distances, we can begin to probe questions about galaxy evolution that you can't otherwise do without having their properties on the scale. We can also look at environment. We can understand whether galaxies are in void whether there are satellites of massive galaxies. This is particularly important with a significant interest in measuring satellite luminosity functions on Milky Way-like analogs. You can't do luminosity function or no is a satellite of a galaxy without knowing its system. It has been pretty impactful in this regime that touches on many science questions. I would be remiss if I didn't mention the Hubble constant. The plot on the right is from the group from last year showing different measurements of the Hubble constant from using T RGB as a distance indicator to calibrate type one supernova. Of course, without HST, we would not be able to do this in the nearby universe. While we might hope that we resolve the tension in the Hubble constant by the time Roman launches, I will remind everyone that we have been doing this for a hundred years. Roman may still have a role to play with distances in a few years' time. Okay. One of the neat things about using Roman to do the distances is that the T RGB gets brighter. This is from some modeling work I did last year that using synthetic bilayer populations, I measured the brightness as a function of wavelength. Here, I'm really focusing on the wavelengths. On the left panel, you have a simple stellar population has some fiducial distance. The T RGB which is color-coded in red is just about at the 21st magnitude. As you move to a Jay band something like a Roman filter, the tip of the red giant is a magnitude brighter. Of the F-2 hundred filter is almost 2 of magnitudes brighter. There are significant observational gains we can get by moving into the thread for distances. The distances are best measured in stellar halos. Showing this example, the distance measured from the sunflower galaxy, the ACS field where the data comes from is highlighted as the white box on the left. It is clearly out away from the stellar disk. It may look like an empty field, on those fields, you end up with a colored magnitude diagram on the right which has over 30,000 stars. The tip of the red giant branch is highlighted with a red marker. We moved to the stellar halos for a number of practical reasons. The first is that stellar halos are less crowded. You can get really high fidelity with less concern about stellar blending. This extinction, that isn't as important, it is still a factor. Probably most importantly, there are fewer young and intermediate ages in the halos. Highlighting one of Ben's slides, you can get helium grown and stars and giant branch

stars that sit in sort of the same region of the color magnitude diagram. Stars can sometimes mask identification of the tip and result in an underestimate of the distance. Moving to the stellar halos, you reduce the number count as demonstrated by this one example. You really do get a clean measurement. One of the other reasons that we go to stellar halos is because we have been thinking for a long time that halos are mostly populated mostly by metal core stars. I mentioned that the filter that we typically do distances and with Hubble only has a modest dependency. As you move to the wavelengths, it increases. Putting something where you think is a metal for field can be important. Except, halos are turning out to be not metal core and show great diversity in their content. This is work done this year. Unless Halo shows the metallicity of the stars as a function of magnitude for elliptical galaxies from dwarf galaxies from dwarf up ellipticals all the way to massive ellipticals. Stellar range from about two decades values. In the upper -- the lowest luminous ellipticals can have a range of metallicity of these in one particular galaxies halo. It represents different galaxies. The spiral shown on the right is an amalgamation of other people's work. While they aren't asked metal rich as ellipticals, they spend quite a range and a particularly but you can notice and 31 has a significant range in that content. FICO from the same modeling work that I did, this is showing the brightness of the T RGBs measured in different filters under different telescopes. The points that are color-coded by the age content. The science points which is a simple stellar population that is very metal core. It spans ranges. Most, there are some changes based on whether the stars on the metal core or metal rich young or old. In the a 14 filter, the points are nearly coincident meaning that they -- the brightness doesn't really change depending on the metal content which is one of the known advantages of this filter. As you move to the near infrared, there brightness of T RGB can actually change by half magnitude depending upon whether the stars are metal poor or not. If you want to be able to use infrared as a precise distance indicator, this really needs to be taken into account. In the same modeling exercise, I was able to calibrate out this metallicity change using the stellar population and the residual change got down to just a couple hundred seven magnitude. Shown here is the difference in that the RG magnitude after this calibration using theoretical ISA Crohn's. 2 minutes left. Thank you. With careful calibration, you can actually get down the variations that are introduced by changes in metal content and age to less than 1% in distance. This last cycle, a new program using data to try to calibrate the near-infrared tip of the red giant's branch as a distance indicator. This is not only going to extend the reach of HST efficiently, but it is the path to preparing for James Webb to be able to do this with filters and looking for to the future with Roman. This is also work that is being done by Max Newman. And records. Looking ahead to Roman, it's going to be this phenomenal telescope for T RGB distances. There is coverage of stellar halos. We saw that in James and Ben's talk at any pointing of a nearby galaxy, you're going to get stellar halos. By default, you will be able to do distances in the field where they are really best done. We'll also be able to get results stars after large distances. The photometric depth is easily reached in Roman. The highlight of community survey that Roman mentioned earlier this morning, from the archive, we will be able to do T RGB distances to nearly any nearby image. I will also say, I serve on the Roman advisory committee. These surveys are still being developed and designed. When you get those emails from the space telescope or any of the organizations asking for input, you know, please take the time to participate. These community surveys are going to be the best surveys with participation from a large part of our community. Thank you.

Thanks very much very much. That was a great talk. We have questions coming in on slack. Again, as questions come in, they will come in a circuit loosely as well. The first question we have our whatever lowest metallicity of these at which T RGB is calibrated.

That is an excellent question. The way it is calibrated it is baked with some -- from the calibrating galaxy. It is set to whatever galaxies used as that calibration. And then, you can adjust using color-based correction. It is empirical feedback loop. If you have a more metal rich galaxy, you can correct it to the calibrating system using the color of the stars. I don't know if it has been tested on exceptionally metal poor galaxies. I am not really sure what range you are asking about. For example, we have used it to calibrate the distance which is about 2% solar. And we got really good agreement between them. Challenge of course is that it is so small and such a low mass that the upper RGB is not fully populated. So there's different challenges inherent like that. We haven't been able to successfully do it down to 2% solar.

Okay, one more question. In the case where you showed as a function of brightness and a larger scatter with the larger galaxies, the metallicity is cities scattered. Is it resolved across the galaxy? Can you account -- can this scatter be accounted for by something else? Why is there a scatter in metallicity?

Okay it is because the upper red giant branch stars luminosity depends on their metal content. And so, a metal poor star will be brighter than a metal rich star just from stellar evolution. And there is a similar but in fact opposite dependency on age. It's a smaller dependency on age but with extreme cases that I modeled, you can actually see the changes with age. It's actually not really scatter. Of the brightness is changing depending upon the luminosity of the star which is dependent upon the metal content.

Thanks a lot, Kristin. That is the time we have for this. Please answer questions on slack.

Our next speaker is **Raja GuhaThakurta**. If you get turn on video and share your slides. Again, our speaker is Raja GuhaThakurta from the University of California Santa Cruz. Please take it away.

Raja: Thanks for the organizers for giving me this talk slot. I want to talk about three science cases for the Nancy Grace Roman space telescope. I'm going to have three science cases listed here. They are local volume galaxies close to home. With the Milky Way. It's a low. Specifically how Roman can help with the measurement of proper motions of distant stars and of course, I will talk a little bit more about the science. If that is measurement. The second thing also has to do with galactic halos. But this time of our neighboring galaxy can really help us as one of the only facilities I can think of that can help us reach the true edge of M31's halo. I will say a little bit about that next. I will spend most of my time talking about globular clusters. It's going to be a fantastic instrument for making progress using these traces of galaxy formation and evolution as tracers of the formation history, chemical enrichment history. The science themes that are common to these three science cases is of course all of our galaxy formation evolution. They address everything from the smallest to the largest galaxies. The largest galaxy we are talking about MAD seven at the center of the cluster, giant elliptical and brightest cluster galaxy. So really the smallest dwarf galaxies including disrupted work galaxies. It will address a range of environments from dents to spars, not the absolute densest, but the cluster is what I will talk about today. Of course, dark matter content, accretion history and chemical enrichment which in turn tells us about the star formation history, the efficiency of star formation and the gas accretion history of these formations. With this background, I'm going to plunge into the first of the science cases. The Milky Way halo. I'm going to talk about a project called halo 70 which is already started. It uses a combination of the existing facilities, the Hubble space telescope, Gaia, and a telescope. And I'm going to talk about what progress Roman can make in this area of science. So the halo 70 survey involves looking at that after a low but also through it to the galaxies. You see a field of distant galaxies. They turn out to be very useful for Milky Way halo science. Before I go any further, the Milky Way halo component, the people involved in that are listed at the bottom. The people who are on the line aren't specifically the young people working on the Milky Way halo component of halo 70. The distant galaxy component is also a team of people working on it in their names are there as well. The references you see at the bottom have to do with a Milky Way halo science some of which has been published and some of which is in prep. So like I said, Hubble archival data is part of a legacy program where we are using multiple Epoque HST imaging and use them as the cosmic wallpaper against which to measure the motion of stars. We intend to do this for about a thousand main sequence stars in the remote Milky Way halo. What I want to say about this project is, it is relevant even in the age of Gaia, because Gaia is studying giants at a great distance. This project is studying garden variety sequence turnoff stars. This Hubble program is supplemented by another program. About a third of those stars -- for starters, we targeted the four candles fields and the M31 foreground as well. He measure radio velocities and we measure chemical abundances. As part of the thesis. We look at the structure based on comparing different lines of sight. As part of their research at Santa Cruz. We've got about 1500 distant galaxies. This worked. I was led by Emily Cunningham as part of her PhD thesis at Santa Cruz last year. At that time and started in Santa Cruz. Now, this is a snippet of result from Emily's work from a paper that came out last year. The different fields as you can see from the lower right hand panel four different lines of sight. Those of you who work on distant galaxies will recognize these fields. You see that the tangential velocity, the dispersion of the radio velocity, the dispersion of the tangential philosophy and the anti-Saturday -- this is something you get when you measure proper motions. These show significant variations in fields the field. Not even a line of sight distance distribution. That's not very well constrained to suggest significant differences. The gist of a relatively recent mergers in the Milky Way halo as other indicators point to as well. What one can do with Roman is deep multi-Epoque Roman pointing's will be absolutely fantastic for measuring the proper motions of stars in the Milky Way halo. The great thing about the Roman field of view is that it is big enough that there are enough stars that you can get a detailed isometric reference frame just using those. And

with repeat imaging with a long enough baseline, one can measure proper motions very efficiently. This is with deep multi-Epoque imaging. I recognize that they won't be as many fields as there will be single Epoque shower fields. The advantage of those is Roman and Gaia can be combined to measure proper motion in a way that extends a couple of magnitudes. Magnitudes beyond what Gaia can measure alone. The advantage is the added baseline. It is the depth and added baseline that Roman plus Gaia gives you compared to Gaia alone. And of course, we don't know exactly what years the Roman observations will take place. For this particular application, the later the better. Gaia observations are going on now. If this would be combined with ground-based telescopes, and again, very excited about what Roman will do in this arena. Moving on to my next science case, I'm going to talk about the outer limits of Andromeda's stellar halo. And I just want to show this one slide here. This is from the paper. The CMD, you see on the left is obtained with hyper supreme cam. The region that is called the Northwest stream. If you can see my cursor, it is the part that is intersecting the hundred K PC radius circle. At this dashed line. Right around there. Of the surface is high enough that you can see a feature on this map. In trying to go further out, and trying to go to 200 or 250-kilo parsecs, it's one of the few instruments that can make a dent. Because when we try to take shallow data out of these radiuses, you can't see it at all. It's too low contrast of this sea of background galaxies. Not so much the foreground stars, because it is really the background galaxies that get you at these large distances. I Roman, you will get the depth to measure the red Giant branch and a horizontal branch and perhaps even the lower part of the red Giant branch with high precision. And it will help that the star galaxies separation of these faint magnitudes can be used to eliminate a lot of the contaminating galaxy. Not all of them. Having multiple filters, one can also use color diagrams to separate stars from galaxies. Very excited about using the outer limits of Andromeda's halo. For my final science case, I want to move to something further out. No longer one mega parsec out like a Andromeda is or 100K PC like that halo is. But more like 15 mega parsecs where the cluster of galaxies is. 2 minutes left. Thank you, that's perfect. In the last 2 minutes, I will talk about something called the next generation cluster survey which is ongoing. Roman is going to make a huge dent here. It is ongoing just on the mega cam imaging in five filters. I listed my collaborators here. Whose work I talked about today is Eric. The names in italics are still high school students who work with us over the years. This background image comes from a wonderful image. All right. Using this existing imaging, what Eric has done is used extremely convoluted methods to use broadband colors and image morphology to select globular clusters and select them from galaxies and stars. This has resulted in the most amazing map of globular clusters in the cluster core. This is the essence of the method in the upper panel. You have inverse concentration which is how fuzzy the object is. Stars are not very fuzzy. And they lie low. Those of the orange. Globular clusters are slightly resolved. You can tell they are slightly more fuzzy than the PSF. Galaxies in general tend to be resolved although there are some compact galaxies. In color space especially if you're going to use the near infrared K band here, best seller is nicely curved. I won't go into the details of why. When you have a curved stellar locus in some color-coded combination draws from that stellar locus combination of stars from that stellar locus tends to land out the locus. That is what the views are. In color space, they separate from stars. They do a reasonable job of separating from reasonable background galaxies as well. Eric has made this amazing map. This is a density map of a globular cluster in the core of Virgo. The Psion... Are known galaxies with their luminosity's marked by the size of the ellipse. You will notice that there are galaxies with a substantial globular cluster population, high-frequency. They are comparable luminosity galaxies that are and they have any globular clusters at all. There is a huge -- there is frequency and the spatial distribution of the globular clusters as well. These are large distributions versus spatially compact. To the end of the stellar light. There are offsets for the globular cluster distributions in highly distorted systems associated with interacting galaxies like these. Roman is going to make and will be an absolute game changer for this type of science. I will say that we are following these globular clusters -- this is where we will continue to do that in the area of the next set of telescopes. We are studying satellites of galaxies as well. What I mean by orphans is when you do this kind of measurement of the velocity of a globular cluster and look at its difference relative to its host, you see a finger around zero. This is R over R effective in affected radius units. These red points are satellites. The blue points are probably contaminants. The black points are a combination of Milky Way stars and orphaned globular clusters on identified. We are very interested in studying those as well. In closing, I will put up my summary slide. I presented three example of local volume galaxies science with the Roman space telescope. The first of those halos of the Milky Way galaxies and Andromeda and M33, I did not talk about and 33. Roman will be good for that. The last science cases globular clusters as dark matter halos, star formation and chemical history of all flavors of galaxies in the cluster environment. Thank you.

Thanks for a great talk. Unfortunately, we are out of time right now for questions. Questions are being asked on slack. If you could login and answer questions they are. Thank you very much. Our next speaker is Sara Pearson. If you get

turn on your video and share your screen, that would be great. I don't see any screen sharing. Potentially the organizers have the presentation, they could bring it up. All right. Maybe it's easier if you share it then. Yeah, I think it's being pulled up. Thanks everyone for a couple of minutes while we sort this out. While we are waiting, I don't know if Susana is on, if you want to tell everyone what the plan is for the break, we could do that.

Sure. In our original plan, I think once Sarah's talk is over, we expect or we encourage everybody to view the posters and talks. You can start by browsing the presenters and titles at the posterior link channel. Once you reach there, you can click on the links and visit individual posterior channels. Feel free to interact with the presenters and their channels. You can do that by chat typing or do audio call. If you have questions for us, you can ask us to ask channel questions. And I hope you have a great closing session after we are done with the talks.

Thank you very much. Russell, if you could play...the screen sharing is about to start. Sara, I would like to introduce. She is a Flatiron Research Fellow. Russell, the screen share -- okay. Take it away.

Sara Pearson: Okay. This will be fun. I'm excited to tell you about something quite specific that we could use to the Roman space telescope for which is to find globular clusters, stellar streams and other galaxies if you could go to the next slide. Okay, stellar streams let me know of roughly 50 stellar streams. We've heard a little bit about how we want to figure out the nature of dark matter from James. One of the reason stellar streams are useful is that they orbit they galaxies and get tightly torn apart and can tell us something about the dark matter distribution in galaxies. If you then click again, yes, the next movie is playing. Another thing they are useful for is that if a dark matter sub halo comes close to the vicinity of a stellar stream, that grow and evolve in the strings. And different descriptions or prescriptions of dark matter dictate that we should have a different distribution of soft halos in galaxies like the Milky Way through studying these gaps induced by dark matter sub halos can be a really useful way of distinguishing the nature of the dark matter particle. Go to the next slide. So one of the problems in our own Milky Way is that there is a lot going on at once. We have molecular clouds, spiral arms, and we have a galactic bar that can all serve to produce these gaps that make it very hard to distinguish whether or not we see a gap in a stream because of an actual dark matter some halo platter coming through or whether or not it is just one of these features. Go to the next slide. So, wouldn't it be great if we could go to other galaxies where we actually don't have galactic bars and click again. So it turns out we actually do as we have seen in many of the talks in this session, we do know of many stellar streams and external galaxies that are not the Milky Way. However, all of these are actually from dwarf galaxies that have fallen in and are now orbiting the host that they are falling into. We actually don't have any clear evidence yet of globular cluster stellar streams around external galaxies. The reason they are particularly useful the search for the nature of dark matter is that they are dynamically cold. They retain the memory of their past very clearly as opposed to the hotter dwarf galaxies streams. If you go to the next slide. So, we want to find these and external galaxies. You can just click one more slide. I love these build outs. So we can use these external galaxies because they are dynamically cold. If we could do that, we could start mapping out the orbit distributions and other galaxies based solely on the morphology of the streams. This is about to publish. Not only that, you can use them to study streams. If we suddenly had a whole population of streams and other galaxies, you can start asking questions about distributions. You can go to the next slide. So, a few people have already shown this. We have courts have our great neighboring galaxy, and 31. M31 does have arms. It's not one of these ideal galaxies for studying gaps. We wanted to ask the question of whether in current data we should actually expect to be able to find globular clusters in another galaxy. You've already seen that there are streams that have been detected that all of these are again from dwarf galaxies. We know that from -- you can click the next slide. Yeah, highlighting this survey. You can go to the next slide again. If you look at this arrow, I am just highlighting the part of the halo that I'm going to investigate in the next couple of slides. I'm taking the longest arrow because there are no clear streams in these arrows. If you go to the next line, I have plotted ten by ten regions along that white arrow. If you look from left to right here on the spot, you are seeing 15K PC and 55K PC from the galactic center of Andromeda. If you go down to the row below, you are cutting away the metal rich stars. We expect globular clusters in order to form stream, we expect them to be old and metal poor. If you go to the next slide. What we did in this recent paper other collaborators was that we took what we know from our own Milky Way which is a very well studied stream. We scaled at length and width based on the title field of Andromeda which is slightly different in the Milky Way. And also based on location at at which we injected this stream. The whole reason we are doing this is to see whether or not we would be able to serve something like that if

it is in the data. We scaled the number of stars we see given five Isaac Brown and given in 30 ones limiting magnitude. We distribute these stars around a great circle. If you go to the next slide. This is highlighting that what you're actually seeing is just the tip of the red Giant branch of something. In the Milky Way, we are catching the turnoff where we would only see the tip of the Giant branch. If you go to the next slide. And, you might as well go to one slide more. Here, we have injected and go one more slide. And something that is ten times its mass. Of those globular clusters that should exist that are more powerful. What you can see here are the take away is that it should be quite hard to observe. Something ten times the mass might actually be detectable in current data. If you go to the next slide. We are currently in searching for these streams in current data. I will get back to that in a second. I wanted to highlight what we could do with the Roman space telescope. If you go one more slide. Okay. The effect was slightly less dramatic now that I can't flip it back and forth and it's not resolved that well here. What you should take away here is that it is very, very easy to actually detect these with the Roman space telescope. This is very exciting already that we know with Roman, we will be able to actually have a whole lot of population of globular clusters streams that we can study in another galaxy. We'd only have the Milky Way as our only data point for now. One more slide. And now, the point you are seeing further out the actual -- due to the magnitudes and go one more slide. Just a few points that are already made. Yeah, I don't have time to go into all of these details of how we do this. We basically scale the background of Andromeda and ask how a given in one hour Roman exposure, how far out can we actually detect these types of stellar streams and galaxies nearby? Depending on what we used for stock galaxies separation if it was a conservative or quite liberal estimate of this, we estimate that roughly we should be able to tax these streams and 200 to roughly 900 galaxies. A lot of these are dwarf galaxies. Globular destructors obviously are not as many of them. We are looking to exactly how many streams we expect to find. It's exciting that we will have a lot more systems to study with Roman. And one more slide. So, just a quick highlight. A graduate student from Princeton is working on extending this method of how many resolved stars we will get given exposure time and different galaxy types. We can more carefully answer these questions. I can go one more slide. Back to how we are actually going to use a newly developed stream transformer code to search for these streams both in current data but also in the future Roman space telescope data. I suggest that you skip ahead. Maybe six slides, because it's all a build. And might be annoying to hear me say skip slide so many times. Yeah, so just keep going. Okay, one back. So if you look at the left input data, you can see that all these different points in a projected x y space. You can imagine those points as being a linear structure is that we use something called a transform of each individual star. As highlighted here with the algorithm. Sorry? I couldn't hear you. I said 2 minutes left. Okay. So in this transfer space, and a linear structure will show up as overlapping. Each single point has its own sinusoidal curve. If you had a lineal structure in whatever you throw it into the code, it will show you as overlapping sinusoids. We can ask at what angles to the sinusoids overlap? The equation on the right side of this slide, you can then recover the linear structure. As you can see very clearly can't detect these streams that happen to be in this image. If you go one more slide. Or two more slides actually. Yeah, just to illustrate what row and data actually are. We have the same data, 45 degrees but different rhos in a different data set of x and y positions. What you can see is that rho kind of determines the impact remedy. How far away from the center where data is the angle at which your structure is. Now, if you go one more slide, I'm almost done. Here, you actually have real data. I have injected three extremes that are the limits that we should see for ten times -- we might actually find these in current data. If you go one more slide. So now, we take and go further, or more slide. We take each of these positions of each star and transform into the transfer space. As you can see, there are clearly three peaks here. If you go on my slide, we can ask our code to locate these picks in rho Theta space and go one more slide. Recover the linear structures one more slide. And find the streams. This is to demonstrate that we can using this transform code that I'm developing using collaborators very efficiently search for structure in current data but also in the future Roman space telescope data. This will enable us to find stream characterize them and very easily see how clearly they stand out against the background and do characteristics of the streams themselves. If you go one more slide. Just point that if we do not find any of these streams in Andromeda, it's already quite interesting that Andromeda should be slightly more massive than the Milky Way and expected to be more globular. There are more globular clusters, we would expect them to be more stellar streams. Go to the next slide and leave out my summary. And very briefly, to summarize, we could use all of these new streams will detect with the Roman space telescope. The orbits and other galaxies and also hopefully figure out a little bit more about the nature of dark matter and this new code that we are writing will enable us to find these streams efficiently. That's all that I have to say.

Thank you for a great talk. Unfortunately, we are out of time right now. If you can log into slack and see questions I have posted there for you, that would be great. I will now hand the session over to the moderators to explain anything else that needs to be discussed. Thank you.

I just want to thank Preethi for chairing this session. It was nicely done. Thanks to all the speakers for today's sessions. Thank you all for attending today's talk sessions. For the next hour or so, I would encourage you to look to the posters and figure out the talks. We have about 40 or 50 of them. And feel free to ask any questions if you have. I will see you all tomorrow for talk session number 3 at t 10:00 a.m. Eastern time. Thank you, have a nice day.

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